

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

TYOLOGY OF AGRICULTURE IN CHERKASY REGION IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

Zozulia I.

*Postgraduate student of the Department
of Ecology and Lifesafety,
Uman National University of Horticulture, Uman
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12571066>*

Abstract

The article is devoted to methodical and methodological aspects of the typology of agriculture in conditions of climate change. The dependence of the ecological state of agriculture landscapes on the specialization of agriculture is considered. The basis of the formation of agricultural specialization in the Cherkasy region is 9 production types of enterprises with numerous subtypes. The result of the agricultural zoning of the Cherkasy region was the allocation of five districts with similar specialization. An analysis of the correspondence of the existing agricultural specialization to the types of natural environment under conditions of climate change was made.

Keywords: production type, agricultural area, agricultural landscapes, balanced nature management, climate change.

Introduction. Climate change is one of the most pressing environmental issues facing humanity. According to the forecasts of leading international climate research centres, over the next century, the temperature will rise by 2-5 degrees Celsius [1]. Agriculture is one of the sectors that is particularly sensitive to the impact of climate change. Agriculture, like no other industry, is closely linked to the intensive use of the main environmental factors – soil, air and water.

The agriculture of the Cherkasy region is very indicative of climate change, as gradual warming has shifted the boundaries of natural zones by almost 100 km to the north, and almost the entire territory of the region is now in the steppe zone [12]. The importance of understanding the consequences of climate change in the regions of old agricultural development, one of which is Cherkasy region, determined the relevance of the research topic.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the main consequences of climate change on the environmental conditions of crop cultivation.

The object of the study is agriculture in Cherkasy region.

The subject of the study is the impact of climate change on the formation of agroecosystems (on the example of Cherkasy region).

Research methods. The foundations of the methodology of production typology and agricultural zoning are laid down in the works of the classics of agricultural

science [11, 2], and have been improved in modern works [6, 8]. One of the studies [7] investigated the types of land use, types of agricultural territory organization, production types of farms and agricultural districts (all by farms) that are being formed in the Kharkiv region.

Given that modern GIS (geographic information systems) have "built-in" methods of spatial interpolation, we used the Thiessen-Voronoi polygons tool to delineate the territory of farms, as it was impossible to obtain real information about the configuration of the farms' territory at this stage of the research due to lack of data [8].

The Voronoi polygon is a set of points in space, each of which is no further from the centre of the space than from other such centres.

The application of this method almost does not lead to spatial distortions of information (while maintaining the principle of reductionism), since farm boundaries "superimposed" on other layers (landscapes, soils, relief, etc.) can together retain the properties of the cartographic model as an analytical tool (Fig. 1).

However, it is possible to clarify the configuration of the territories of individual farms using land cadastre data [5], but it will require time-consuming mapping procedures, which the author hopes to implement in the near future [14].

Figure 1. Spatial interpolation of farm boundaries using Voronoi polygons.

Research results. Using information on each farm [4], we identified the production types of agricultural enterprises. As of the end of 2020, 378 agricultural enterprises operated in the Cherkasy region, specialising mainly in crop production. In total, 9 production types of farms were identified in the region in terms of the ratio of specialisation sectors. The main types were formed by grain farming, cultivation of industrial oilseeds, and meat and dairy cattle breeding. The formation of subtypes was most influenced by pig breeding, dairy and meat cattle breeding, beet growing and other industries such as sheep breeding, poultry farming, and horticulture.

The first most important production area "Crop farms" accounts for 194 farms with the following types: 1) Grain farming (cereals, legumes and corn); 2) Grain farming (corn cultivation); 3) Growing industrial crops; 4) Grain farming and horticulture.

In accordance with the main production types, subtypes are formed in combination: 1a) with technical (soybean, sunflower, rapeseed); 1b) with technical oilseeds; 1c) with technical (sunflower, soybean); 1d) with technical (soybean, sugar beet); 1e) with technical (soybean); 1f) with technical crops, potato growing and vegetable growing; 1g) with technical crops in various combinations; 1h) with vegetable growing; 1i) with industrial crops (sugar beet); 2a) with industrial oilseeds; 2b) with sugar beet; 2c) with industrial crops in various combinations; 3a); 3b) industrial oilseeds with soybeans; 3c) soybean cultivation; 3d) soybeans with potato and vegetable cultivation;

Type 6, "Grain farming, cultivation of industrial crops and livestock", is the most "variegated" with eleven separate areas forming the respective subtypes. We explain this "diversity" by a certain desire of the management of the respective farms to be self-sufficient, since it is very difficult to achieve economic efficiency in the development of each of its sub-sectors in the presence of extensive livestock production.

Livestock farms in their "pure" form are represented only by poultry farms.

The analysis of the distribution of enterprises across the territory of Cherkasy region confirms compliance (or non-compliance) with the main natural and economic patterns. Thus, the majority of grain farms are "tied" to the flat areas of the central part of the region. The Prydniprovia districts of the region are developing a consumer-oriented specialisation (Cherkasy) and relying on significant irrigation resources - open-ground vegetables, dairy and meat cattle breeding, and poultry farming. Only in the western regions of the Uman "bush" is the most complex crop and livestock specialization developing, which is explained by the certain autonomy of this territory.

The logical extension of the production typology is agricultural zoning. An agricultural district is a relatively homogeneous area in terms of natural resources, where similar agricultural specialization is developing [5,6,10].

On the basis of the allocation of production types, as well as taking into account the landscape diversity [3], we have identified the following agricultural areas in the region (Fig. 2).

I. Prydniprovya-Cherkasy district (comprising the territories of Cherkasy, Zolotonosha, Chornobaiv, Drabiv, eastern part of Horodyshe, northern part of Smila, eastern part of Chyhyryn administrative districts) with high-intensity agriculture of valley-suburban (azonal) type with specialisation in crop production on Grain farming, fodder production, open-air vegetable growing, horticulture; in livestock farming: dairy and meat cattle breeding, pig breeding, poultry farming.

II. Central Forest-Steppe (comprising the territories of Kaniv, Korsun-Shevchenkivskiy, Zvenyhorodkivskiy, Lysianskyi, northern part of Horodyschenskyi and northern part of Shpolianskyi administrative districts) with intensive zonal agriculture with predominant specialisation in crop production (grain farming combined with cultivation of various technical, mainly oilseeds) and less developed livestock (pig and meat and dairy cattle breeding).

III. Southern Forest-Steppe (comprising the territories of the southern and western parts of Chyhyrinskyi, all of Kamianskyi, southern part of Smilyanskyi central and southern parts of Shpolyansky and all of Katerynopilsky administrative districts) with medium-intensive zonal agriculture with a predominant specialisation in crop production (developed grain farming with lesser importance of industrial crops) and livestock farming of a mixed (self-sufficient) type (cattle, pig, sheep, beekeeping, poultry farming).

IV. North-Western Forest-Steppe (comprising the territories of Zhashkiv, Monastyryshche and Mankiv administrative districts) with medium-intensive zonal agriculture with a predominant specialisation in crop

production (grain farming and cultivation of various industrial crops) and semi-extensive livestock farming (dairy and meat cattle breeding with a feedlot-stall type of livestock keeping and pig farming as an auxiliary industry).

V. South-Western Forest-Steppe (comprising the territories of Talniv, Uman and Khrystyniv administrative districts) with highly intensive zonal agriculture of the crop-livestock type with specialisation in crop production in: grain farming and cultivation of industrial (mainly oilseeds) crops; in livestock production in intensive dairy, meat and dairy cattle breeding and pig breeding.

Establishing the correspondence of agricultural specialization to the types of natural environment requires special more detailed studies (mainly expeditionary) using data from specific farms. However, it is also possible to establish general patterns of distribution of certain types of agriculture by analyzing the map of agricultural districts we have created (Fig. 2).

For example, the central part of the forest-steppe zone of Cherkasy region is characterised by zonal production types of farms based on grain farming and meat and dairy cattle breeding. In the transition to the southern forest-steppe, this type is complemented by developed pig breeding and production of industrial crops. However, this type is highly susceptible to local influences, which are expressed in the action of economic factors, such as large settlements (district centres), as well as agricultural processing enterprises (Shpola, Vattino, Kamyanka, Katerynopil).

Figure 2. Agricultural districts being formed in Cherkasy region (names of districts in the text).

In the forest-steppe landscapes of the western part of Cherkasy oblast, the type with grain farming and meat and dairy cattle breeding is transforming into a type with a greater representation of dairy and meat cat-

tle breeding (probably due to the increase in the structure of feeding rations of juicy fodder from the pastures of the Gornyi Tikych, Ruda, Syniukha, and Yatran rivers). However, the unclear differentiation of natural factors in the transition from the forest-steppe to the

steppe zone (Southern Forest-Steppe region) causes an equally unclear change in specialisation. Thus, in the southern farms of the region, grain farming with meat and dairy cattle breeding is complemented by pig, sheep, bee and poultry farming as additional (self-sufficient) industries. It is important to note that in this area (III), specialisation is being formed that is more typical of the steppe zone, which has a logical explanation in some studies that note the "pushing" of the steppe and forest-steppe zone boundaries to the north due to global climate warming.

Global climate change naturally causes the boundaries of natural zones to move, intensifies ecotonization (blurring of landscape boundaries) of the land surface, and therefore inevitably leads to the correction of zonal specialization of agricultural production [9]. We set out to study these phenomena on the example of Cherkasy region, which is located in the heart of our country and has an agricultural specialisation in the all-Ukrainian territorial division of labour. In the context of climate change, which adjusts the natural prerequisites for zonal specialisation of agriculture, we clarify their names in this paper (Fig. 2):

1) Prydniprovsko-Cherkasy (mainly comprising the territories of the modern enlarged Zolotonosha and northern part of Cherkasy administrative districts) with high-intensity agriculture of valley-suburban (azonal) type with specialisation in crop production in grain farming, fodder production, open-air vegetable growing, horticulture; in livestock production - in dairy and meat cattle breeding, pig breeding, poultry farming;

2) Central forest-steppe (mainly within the majority of the present-day enlarged Zvenyhorod administrative district) with intensive zonal agriculture with a predominant specialisation in crop production (grain farming combined with the cultivation of various industrial, mainly oilseeds) and less developed livestock farming (pig and meat and dairy cattle breeding);

3) Southern transitional from forest-steppe to steppe (comprising the territories of the southern parts of Zvenyhorod and Cherkasy amalgamated administrative districts) with medium-intensive zonal agriculture with predominant specialisation in crop production (developed grain farming with lesser importance of industrial crops) and mixed (self-sufficient) livestock (cattle, pig, sheep, beekeeping, poultry);

4) North-Western Forest-Steppe (the territory of the northern part of the enlarged Uman Administrative District) with medium-intensity zonal agriculture with a predominant specialization in crop production (grain farming and cultivation of various industrial crops) and semi-extensive livestock production (dairy and meat cattle breeding with a feedlot-stall type of livestock keeping and pig breeding as an auxiliary industry);

5) South-Western transition from forest-steppe to steppe (comprising the southern part of Uman and south-western Zvenyhorod enlarged administrative districts) with high-intensity zonal agriculture of crop-livestock type with specialisation in crop production on grain farming and cultivation of technical (mainly oilseeds) crops; in livestock production - on intensive dairy, meat and dairy cattle breeding and pig breeding. It is important to note that in the third and fifth districts

we have identified, specialisation is being formed that is more typical of the steppe zone, which, according to researchers, is explained by the northward movement of the border between the forest-steppe and steppe zones due to global climate warming [10].

Conclusions and recommendations. Based on the analysis of the boundaries of agricultural districts formed in the Cherkasy region, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Despite the significant influence of market factors, the zonal-belt types of agricultural landscapes in their distribution repeat the zonal-belt geography of natural landscapes (as can be seen from the configuration of the central forest-steppe regions). Regarding the possibilities of coincidence of natural and agricultural zoning, classical works in this area note that such coincidence is observed quite often, but this cannot be a general rule.

2. The conducted typology and agricultural zoning of the Cherkasy region can be the basis for assessing the harmful environmental impact on agricultural landscapes of certain specialisation sectors, in particular in the context of climate change [13].

3. The conducted typology and agricultural zoning is only the first step towards understanding the level of ecological correspondence of the existing specialisation to certain natural landscapes and only outlines the true situation in general terms. The next step is to determine the specialisation of peasant (homestead) farms, since they are at the lowest level of spatial organisation of natural ecosystems and largely operate on the principles of subsistence farming.

The author sees the prospects for the development of the direction outlined in this article in clarifying the specialization of individual farms using data from expeditionary research, as well as land cadastre data using special economic and mathematical methods. Upon completion of the above research procedures, it is possible to create a specialized geographic information system (GIS), which can become an effective tool for improving the ecological state of agriculture and regulating land relations in Cherkasy Oblast in the context of climate change.

References:

1. Melnichenko L.V., Petrovsky V.G., Impact of climate change on agroecosystems. / Collection of abstracts of the III International Scientific and Practical Conference "Climate Change and Agriculture. Challenges for Agricultural Science and Education", June 2020. Scientific and Methodological Centre of the VFPO. Kyiv, 2020. 28-31.

2. Mukomel I.F. Agricultural zones of the Ukrainian SSR, part 1. Kyiv: KSU, 1954. 107.

3. Report on the development of the regional scheme of the ecological network of Cherkasy region, 2019. URL: <http://eco.ck.ua>.

4. Kolosok.info. URL: kolosok.info, <https://tripoli.land/>

5. Kadastrova-karta. URL: <http://www.map.dazru.gov.ua/kadastrova-karta>

6. Sonko S.P. Agroecosystem as an ecological niche of a person. Ч.1. Agronomy. Issue 71. Uman. 2009. 188-199,
7. Sonko S.P. Production typology of agriculture in Kharkiv region: thirty years later." Journal of Socio-Economic Geography: Interregional collection of scientific papers. Kharkiv, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, 2015. Issue 19 (2). 30-39.
8. Sonko S.P. Experience of creating an elementary GIS "Assessment of the environmental impact of agriculture on the landscapes of Cherkasy region": Materials of the scientific conference.- Uman: Vizavi, 2015. 18-23.
9. Sonko S.P., Kiselev Y.O. Agricultural zoning of Cherkasy region in the context of global climate change: Proceedings of the IV International Scientific and Practical Conference [Kherson, 10-11 June 2021]. Kherson: KHSAEU, 2021. 279-283.
10. Agricultural zoning is the first step towards balanced nature management in the agrosphere. Bulletin of the Uman National University of Horticulture, No. 1. 2015. 106-112.
11. Kostrowicki J. The Typology of Word Agriculture, Warsaw, 1974.
12. Sonko S. P. Express assessment of environmental impact of agriculture technologies on the soils of Cherkasy Oblast. Ukrainian Journal of Ecology, 2018, 8(1). 451-459 doi:10.15421/2017_235.
13. Zozulia Ivan. Increasing phytodiversity of agroecosystems - the path of adaptation to climate change. / Climate change and agriculture. Challenges for agrarian science and education: collection of materials of the VII International Scientific and Practical Conference, 27 March 2024, Scientific and Methodological Centre of the VFPO. Kyiv, 2024. 63-66.
14. Zozulia Ivan, Sonko Sergiy. Modern approaches to monitoring the environmental impact of agriculture on agriculture landscapes (on the example of farms in the Cherkasy region). / Current issues of formal and non-formal education in environmental monitoring and conservation: Abstracts of III International Internet Conference (Kharkiv, April 26, 2024). Kharkiv: V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, 2024. 167.